

Energy harvesting analysis of structural composite utilizing contact electrification and electrostatic induction

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Introduction

● Research background

Smart Structural Composite

Functions

- Light weight & high strength
- Strain sensing
- Energy storage
- Self-healing, self-heating
- Electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding
- Energy harvesting

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Introduction

- Research motivation
- Need to develop technologies to capture and utilize mechanical energy from structures

Abundant Mechanical Energy

Structural Energy Harvester
- TENG tile, TENG road..

Semi-permanent Energy Harvesting

Introduction • Objective

- Inventing self-powering structural composite
- Utilize
 - 1) the existing structure of carbon fiber reinforced plastic, which contains both conductive and dielectric materials
 - 2) a triboelectric nanogenerator mechanism that converts mechanical energy into electrical energy

Introduction

● Working mechanism of triboelectric nanogenerator (TENG)

1) Triboelectrification

2) Electrostatic induction

- TENG works with the coupling of triboelectrification and electrostatic induction

Introduction

- Fabrication and experimental setup

Result

- Optical microscopy image of cross section of PWCF/PA6 composite

Result

• Energy harvesting performance of carbon fiber/PA6 composite

• Analyzing a single voltage signal

- A negative voltage was generated when they are in contact, and a positive voltage was generated when they are separated.

Result

● Voltage depending on press force

Tapping distance : 10 mm
Frequency : 1 Hz

- From 10 N to 80 N, voltage gradually increased.

Result

● Voltage, short-circuit current depending on tapping speed

Tapping distance : 10 mm
Pressing force : 70 N

- Voltage and short-circuit current increased as tapping frequency increased.

Result

● Current and power density depending on resistance

Tapping distance : 10 mm
Frequency : 5 Hz
Pressing force : 70 N

$P = IR^2$

- When a resistance of 20 MΩ was connected, power density of 513.5 μW/cm² was generated.

Result

● Voltage variation with prolonged contact-separation

Tapping distance : 10 mm
Frequency : 3 Hz
Pressing force : 70 N

- Peak output voltage increased gradually from 220 V to 267 V for 5100 sec.

Result

● Verification of feasibility of utilizing generated electrical energy

• Rectification

• Turning on LEDs

• Energy storage

Conclusion

- To capture the mechanical energy generated by the structure, the triboelectrification was applied to the structural material, carbon fiber reinforced plastic.
- Confirmed that changes in voltage, current, and charge occurred in the CFRP and that the amount of electrical energy increased with increasing pressing force and speed.
- A power density of $513.5 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ was generated when a resistor of $20 \text{ M}\Omega$ was connected, and it was observed that the generated voltage increased with prolonged contact and separation.
- The electrical energy generated by the composite was rectified and stored, and the LEDs were turned on to verify the energy utilization potential.

Thank you!

Supporting information

Theoretical basis

V : Electric potential difference

ϵ_0 : vacuum permittivity (8.854×10^{-12} F m⁻¹)

ϵ_r : dielectric constant

σ_c : Surface static charge areal density

$\sigma(z)$: Transferred charge density

$E_1 = \frac{\sigma(z)}{\epsilon_1}$		$V = \sigma(z) \left[\frac{d_1}{\epsilon_1} + \frac{d_2}{\epsilon_2} \right] + \frac{z[\sigma(z) - \sigma_c]}{\epsilon_0}$
$E_2 = \frac{\sigma(z)}{\epsilon_2}$		<p>Under short-circuit condition, $V = 0$</p>
$E_{\text{gap}} = \frac{\sigma(z) - \sigma_c}{\epsilon_0}$		$\sigma(z) = \frac{z\sigma_c}{\frac{d_1\epsilon_0}{\epsilon_1} + \frac{d_2\epsilon_0}{\epsilon_2} + \epsilon_0}$
$V = E_1 d_1 + E_2 d_2 + E_{\text{gap}} z$		